

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Abimbola****FIRST NAME: Oladiran****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied U.S. U.K. conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did not use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did not use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: MSWord 2019 on Windows 10

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. The introduction also has three aims. It should not ____?
 - Put your research in the context of other research.
 - Make readers understand how your paper addresses a problem they care about.
 - Present an argument to the readers.**¹
 - Give readers a framework for understanding the research.
2. Research questions should ____?
 - Be answerable with a simple yes or no**²
 - Confront prevailing assumptions

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 110.

² Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, (Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications Inc, 2018), 309.

- Be directly tied to the study purpose
 - Be clear, specific, and unambiguously stated
3. What are the essential components that should be included in a problem statement for a research study?
- Theoretical and/or practical importance, research funding agencies, population demographics, and research design.
 - Theoretical and/or practical importance, type of research, population to be investigated and rationale, and elements/factors involved.**³
 - Theoretical and/or practical importance, data collection tools, sample size, and statistical power.
 - Theoretical and/or practical importance, research ethics guidelines, participant consent, and data analysis techniques.
4. Which of the following are not key components of a methodology chapter?
- Introduction and overview, research sample, an overview of the information needed.
 - Research design, research purpose, limitations, and delimitations of the study.**⁴
 - Methods for data analysis and synthesis, ethical considerations, research sample.
 - Issues of trustworthiness, chapter summary, methods of data collection.

³ Bloomberg and Volpe, 311.

⁴ Bloomberg and Volpe, 435–38.

5. Which one of these sentences demonstrates the correct use of a hyphen?
- The tutor asked me to send her an e-mail
 - John has a finely tuned ear for off-key music.**⁵
 - Jane was a highly-respected professor.
 - Linda wasn't a top-drawer.
6. According to the English style guide, if all items are complete statements without a grammatical link to the introductory sentence, one should not ____?
- Introduce the list with a colon.
 - Start each item with an upper-case letter.**⁶
 - End each one with a semicolon.
 - Put a full stop at the end.
7. Which of the following would you fail to consider when formulating a research argument?
- Building the argument around answers to the reader's questions.
 - Developing a claim from a working hypothesis.
 - Preferring arguments based on warrants to arguments based on evidence.**⁷

⁵ Cleenewerck Laurent and Gulma Kabiru, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 36.

⁶ European Commission, *English Style Guide*, 2021, 57–58, https://commission.europa.eu/sites/default/files/styleguide_english_dgt_en.pdf.

⁷ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 66.

- Adding a warrant to your argument when you think a reader might reject your claim.
8. Which of the following is not a key factor in determining the reasonableness of a research recommendation?
- Being logically and clearly derived from the findings.
- Being generalizable to multiple contexts.** ⁸
- Being both content and context-specific.
- Being practical and capable of implementation.
9. The following are key considerations when paraphrasing information from an author in your writing. Except?
- The language you use cannot resemble the words of the author.
- The writing style you use to express the author's ideas must be similar to the style the author used.** ⁹
- The information that you are providing must be an accurate representation of what the author originally wrote.
- You must still cite the work when the information came from, even after paraphrasing.

⁸ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 680.

⁹ Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 36.

10. Which of the following citations follow the notes-bibliography style? [Notes are identified with an N and Bibliographies with a B].

Book Title.

- **N:** 1. Angela Duckworth, *Grit: The Power of Passion and Perseverance*. (New York: Scribner, 2016), 82.
- **B:** Duckworth, Angela. *Grit: The Power of Passion and Perseverance*. New York: Scribner, 2016.

Single Chapter in an Edited Book

- **N:** 1. Kelly Gillespie, “Before the Commission: Ethnography as Public Testimony,” in *If Truth Be Told: The Politics of Public Ethnography*, ed. Didier Fassin (Durham, NC: Duke University Press, 2017), 72.
- **B:** Gillespie, Kelly. “Before the Commission: Ethnography as Public Testimony.” In *If truth be told: The politics of public ethnography*, edited by Didier Fassin, 69–95. Durham, NC: Duke University Press, 2017.

Journal Article

- **N:** 1. Ben Mercer, “Specters of Fascism: The Rhetoric of Historical Analogy in 1968,” *Journal of Modern History* 88, no. 1 (March 2016): 98.
- **B:** Ben Mercer. “Specters of Fascism: The Rhetoric of Historical Analogy in 1968.” *Journal of Modern History* 88, no. 1 (March 2016): 96–129.

Book Title.

- **N:** 1. Jane Austen, *Mansfield Park: An Annotated Edition*, ed. Deidre Shauna Lynch (Cambridge, MA: Belknap Press of Harvard University Press, 2016), 223–24.

- **B: Austen, Jane. *Mansfield Park: An Annotated Edition*. Edited by Deidre Shauna Lynch. Cambridge, MA: Belknap Press of Harvard University Press, 2016.**¹⁰

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda D., and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications Inc, 2018

European Commission. *English Style Guide*, 2021.
https://commission.europa.eu/sites/default/files/styleguide_english_dgt_en.pdf.

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Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

¹⁰ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 151–52.